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Abstract

The majority of Pangandaran Regency’s population consists of Sundanese ethnic groups. However, transmigration and the development of railway access to Pangandaran. Such migration has inevitably influenced the sociocultural and linguistic dynamics of the area. This study aims to trace the migration of the Javanese ethnic group through the mapping of linguistic distribution and variation in Pangandaran Regency. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative method was used to analyze relationships between linguistic variables through dialectometric calculations, while the qualitative method provided insights into the sociolinguistic landscape of the region based on those calculations. The study integrates dialectological and sociolinguistic perspectives. Field findings indicate that the most prominent linguistic mapping falls within the two-etymon category, suggesting the presence of two distinct languages in Pangandaran: Sundanese and Javanese. Furthermore, isogloss bundles and spider-web maps highlight clusters of lexical variation predominantly located in the eastern, southern, and southwestern parts of the regency. These dialectometric-based variations clearly delineate the linguistic boundary between Sundanese and Javanese. Sundanese is spoken across nearly all areas, appearing in 20 observation points, while Javanese is present in only 5 points. Interviews reveal that the Javanese language was introduced by migrant communities who settled in the highland regions and along the railway corridor.

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Keywords

dialectology, language variation, linguistic distribution, Pangandaran, sociolinguistic

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Introduction

Pangandaran Regency is situated in West Java Province and shares a direct border with Cilacap Regency in Central Java Province. As a border area, Pangandaran presents a unique linguistic landscape shaped by the contact between two major languages: Sundanese and Javanese. This language convergence makes Pangandaran an ideal site for examining language contact and distribution phenomena. Djajasudarma et al. (1994), in their study, observed that the linguistic situation in Pangandaran tends toward acculturation between Sundanese and non-Sundanese languages, including Javanese, Indonesian, and several foreign languages. They noted that this acculturation stems from ongoing language contact, especially considering Pangandaran's status as a prominent tourism area in West Java. The geographical position of Pangandaran thus plays a significant role in shaping its linguistic dynamics.

In addition, Mulatsih (2014) provided a different perspective on language contact in Pangandaran. She noted that although the majority of the population in the regency is Sundanese, a key political policy during the New Order era—transmigration and population equalization across Indonesia—resulted in significant Javanese migration into the region. Supporting this, Indira et al. (2019) documented that the migration of the Javanese population to Pangandaran began in the early 20th century. They argued that this movement was driven by the availability of employment in coconut plantations and the establishment of a railway line connecting to Pangandaran. These migration flows have directly influenced the region's sociocultural and linguistic dynamics. During this period, developments in transportation and communication systems enabled broader social change, including shifts in language distribution and intensified language contact between Sundanese and non-Sundanese groups, particularly Javanese.

Drawing on these findings, the present study aims to examine the traces of Javanese migration into Pangandaran and explore how such movements have shaped the linguistic dynamics of this border region. In addition to analyzing language variation, this research investigates the distribution of Javanese speakers and their interactions with Sundanese-speaking communities.

Previous studies in dialectology have laid a strong foundation for this field, such as the work by Saddhono & Hartanto (2021) Klaten Regency which is influenced by Yogyakarta and Surakarta isolect. This is a quantitative descriptive study. Our data was collected from the residents of Wedi District, Klaten. The data was collected from 15 points of observation areas (villages, who conducted a dialectological analysis of the isogloss status of Yogyakarta and Surakarta. Their study, which employed a descriptive quantitative approach with observation and interview techniques, utilized lexical and phonological dialectometry. They concluded that linguistic differences ranged from minor lexical distinctions to substantial dialectal divergences. Their combined lexical and phonological permutation calculations supported these findings, showing a broad spectrum of Javanese isolect diversity in Wedi District.

While their study focused on dialectal distinctions, the present research offers a distinct contribution by exploring not only linguistic variation but also interlingual interaction and

language contact in Pangandaran. In this way, it aims to advance dialectological studies while contributing to language mapping efforts that document the current linguistic conditions in Pangandaran Regency.

A relevant linguistic study in the region was conducted by Mulatsih (2014), who found that Pangandaran’s population generally exhibits multilingual and diglossic tendencies, with language use varying by domain. Her study also revealed widespread code-switching and code-mixing behaviors, while notably observing no signs of language shift. The prevailing language use patterns pointed to a strong degree of language maintenance in this multilingual context.

What sets the present study apart from Mulatsih’s (2014) work is its methodological and analytical framework. Whereas Mulatsih adopted a qualitative sociolinguistic approach, this study combines dialectological analysis with both quantitative and qualitative methods. Furthermore, building upon her findings, this research deepens the exploration of linguistic distribution and variation to trace Javanese migration patterns within Pangandaran. It expands the scope beyond tourism and geography to also consider historical factors. This study encompasses a broader range of observation points—25 in total—covering all districts in Pangandaran Regency. Such an extensive fieldwork design enhances the validity of the linguistic portrait presented in this research.

Moreover, this study has several significant contributions. Academically, it enriches dialectological scholarship by providing empirical data on language boundaries in a linguistically complex border region. From a policy perspective, it offers practical insights, especially considering that Sundanese is the only local language formally taught in schools throughout Pangandaran—even in villages with predominantly Javanese populations. This policy has implications for local identity and may lead to gradual language shift. Therefore, the study’s findings may inform language education policy and support language maintenance strategies for regional languages at risk. In doing so, this research not only contributes to theoretical linguistics but also offers practical guidance for managing linguistic diversity in Indonesia.

Literature Review

Dialectology

Dialectology is a subfield of linguistics concerned with the study of dialects or regional language variation (Boberg et al., 2018). The discipline of dialectology originated simultaneously in two distinct locations. In Germany, George Wenker initiated dialectological work to test the comparative-historical linguistic theory related to the principle of sound laws without exceptions. Concurrently, in France, Gaston Paris began his work by creating phonetic maps of dialects across France in 1875 (Chambers & Trudgill, 2004). The two scholars employed different methods for collecting linguistic data: Wenker distributed surveys assisted by research aides, while Paris collected data directly through field interviews with informants. This study adopts a data collection method similar to that of Gaston Paris, allowing for more accurate data gathering and the potential discovery of additional sociolinguistic insights in the field.

Language mapping is a useful tool for observing linguistic variation across regions. Campbell and Mixco (Fathira, 2018) define language maps as geographic visualizations that depict the distribution of specific languages or distinctive linguistic features in a particular area. In this study, language maps are used to illustrate the distribution of lexical variation, language status, and lexical borrowing across the research area. Ayatrohaedi (2002) outlines three stages in the process of language mapping: (a) creating maps and populating them with symbols and labels, (b) publishing the maps, and (c) discussing the maps' implications. Additionally, he emphasizes the need to prepare three types of maps—base maps, independent maps, and reconstruction maps—prior to symbol and label insertion.

To identify language and dialect differences within a region, the use of isoglosses is essential. The term isogloss was introduced in 1892 by J.G.A. Bielenstein, a dialectologist (Fathira, 2018). The word isogloss derives from the Greek *iso* (equal) and *gloss* (language), meaning “same in language.” Ayatrohaedi (2002) defines isoglosses as lines that separate one linguistic feature from another. When multiple isoglosses overlap, they form what is known as an isogloss bundle. Dominant isogloss lines on a language map can reveal partial patterns of language distribution and highlight areas with similar linguistic phenomena.

Dialectometry is used to classify linguistic varieties by quantifying differences in speech, subdialects, dialects, or languages. This quantitative approach was introduced by Jean Séguy (Lauder, 2007). Séguy's method involves a formulaic calculation of linguistic distance between speech varieties.

Guitier and Lauder offer differing perspectives on how to categorize language varieties based on dialectometric results. Guitier (Lauder, 2007) proposed a classification that was later adapted by Lauder (1993) to better reflect the linguistic context of Indonesia. The table below outlines the distinctions between Guitier's and Lauder's thresholds for language differentiation.

Table 1. Dialectometric Classification Thresholds

Category	Guitier (1973)	Lauder (1993)
Different language	>80%	≥70%
Different dialect	51–80%	51–69%
Different subdialect	31–50%	41–50%
Different speech style	21–30%	31–40%
No significant difference	<20%	≤30%

Based on the comparison above, this study applies the classification system proposed by Lauder. The rationale is that Lauder's thresholds are more suitable and relevant for Indonesia's sociolinguistic context. Using Guitier's classification would suggest that Indonesia has only one language, as linguistic difference must exceed 80% to be considered a separate language. However, field observations show otherwise; for example, Javanese speakers generally do not understand Sundanese, and vice versa, even when the percentage of lexical difference falls below 80%.

Migration and Language Contact

Migration is one of the main factors that triggers language contact, as human movement brings speakers from different linguistic backgrounds into the same social space. When migrant groups settle in a new region, daily social interaction with the local community creates linguistic contact that facilitates the exchange of linguistic elements and the adaptation of language practices. Language contact can be understood as a social process influenced by social relations, economic conditions, and the intensity of interaction between speaker groups (Deumert, 2006; Hansen, 2020). Migration also increases linguistic diversity in the destination region and can result in the development of language varieties within migrant communities as a form of adaptation to the new social and linguistic environment (Capstick, 2020; Deprez, 2006).

Within migrant communities, language contact often yields various linguistic consequences such as bilingualism, code-switching, language shift, or the preservation of heritage languages. The practices of bilingualism and code-switching frequently emerge as communication strategies when speakers must adapt to a different linguistic environment (Auyeskan, 2025; Schmid, 2005). However, the dominance of the majority language in the destination region can also drive language shift in the long term, particularly among subsequent generations (Jansen, 2013; Medford, 2024). Nevertheless, language also serves as a marker of social identity for migrant communities; consequently, in some cases, the language of origin is retained as a symbol of identity and group solidarity (Atindogbé & Endurance, 2023; Olariu, 2020). This framework is relevant for understanding the linguistic distribution in Pangandaran Regency, particularly the presence of a Javanese-speaking community in Wonoharjo Village, which demonstrates how historical migration can create pockets of minority languages amidst the dominance of Sundanese.

Metodology

This study adopts a dialectological approach (Chambers & Trudgill, 2004), which is employed to investigate language variation within a specific geographic area through language mapping. Language mapping is conducted by constructing linguistic maps, isoglosses, and bundles of isoglosses to identify dialect usage within the framework of dialectological studies (Lauder, 2007). The methodological design integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The qualitative method is used to capture social phenomena related to language contact and variation, while the quantitative method facilitates systematic measurement through dialectometric analysis (Afrizal, 2016).

In dialectometric analysis, 317 lexical items collected from 25 observation points were compared across locations to determine whether the forms used were the same or different. The results of these comparisons were then converted into numerical values representing the degree of linguistic difference between the two locations being compared. The dialectometric distance is calculated using the percentage difference formula, namely the number of different items divided by the total number of items compared, then multiplied by one hundred to obtain a percentage value. This value illustrates the degree of linguistic

distance between the two observation points. The higher the percentage difference, the greater the linguistic distance between the two regions.

This mixed-methods approach is appropriate for the research objectives, enabling the analysis of relationships between linguistic variables as well as the explanation of the social and historical factors underlying these relationships.

The data for this study consist of lexical items directly elicited from informants and transcribed phonetically using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). However, for the Sundanese phoneme /eu/, the study uses [ö] based on Sundanese transliteration conventions, rather than the IPA symbol [y]. Data collection was conducted through interviews and direct observation. The interview instrument comprised a 200-item Swadesh list (Chambers & Trudgill, 2004), supplemented with a culturally basic vocabulary list, organized by semantic fields, which included 98 motion and action verbs and 25 function words. The inclusion of culturally basic vocabulary is based on the assumption that these lexical items are more susceptible to change across languages (Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa, 2018).

To ensure data validity, the study employed data triangulation by comparing responses from multiple informants and cross-checking with other sources such as regional language dictionaries and previous studies.

Informants were selected using purposive sampling, based on criteria established by Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa (2018). Ideal informants were adult males aged approximately 20–50 years, born and raised in the same village as their parents and grandparents, with relatively low levels of formal education and low socioeconomic mobility, mentally and physically healthy, and able to speak Indonesian. Additionally, several informants over the age of 50 were included, provided they demonstrated clear and complete articulation, under the assumption that older speakers would preserve more distinct features of traditional dialects less influenced by external linguistic contact.

Fieldwork was conducted in all ten subdistricts of Pangandaran Regency, West Java Province: Cimerak, Cijulang, Cigugur, Langkaplancar, Parigi, Sidamulih, Pangandaran, Kalipucang, Padaherang, and Mangunjaya. From these subdistricts, 25 observation points were selected, with 2 to 3 points in each. The selection of observation points was based on the distribution of Javanese and Sundanese speakers, as well as the distinction between older and newer settlements, referencing the 2018 Village Potential Data of Pangandaran Regency. This distribution is expected to help delineate linguistic boundaries within the regency.

Table 2. Numbering of Pangandaran Regency Map

Number of Map	Village	Sub-District	Number of Map	Village	Sub-District
1.	Paledah	Padaherang	14.	Kertamukti	Cimerak
2.	Bagolo	Kalipucang	15.	Mekarsari	Cimerak
3.	Cibanten	Cijulang	16.	Jangraga	Mangunjaya
4.	Cintakarya	Parigi	17.	Pananjung	Pangandaran
5.	Padaherang	Padaherang	18.	Batukaras	Cijulang
6.	Banjarharja	Kalipucang	19.	Cimerak	Cimerak
7.	Wonoharjo	Pangandaran	20.	Pagerbumi	Cigugur
8.	Sidamulih	Sidamulih	21.	Harumandala	Cigugur
9.	Sukaresik	Sidamulih	22.	Mekarwangi	Langkaplancar
10.	Parigi	Parigi	23.	Karangkamiri	Langkaplancar
11.	Cikalong	Cimerak	24.	Kerjaya	Cigugur
12.	Pagergunung	Langkaplancar	25.	Maruyungsari	Padaherang
13.	Pangandaran	Pangandaran			

The numbering pattern for the observation sites follows a clockwise circular pattern, beginning from the periphery and moving inward. This pattern reflects both historical and geographical considerations in Pangandaran Regency, where immigrant populations are predominantly located in upland areas and along former railway lines (Kabupaten Pangandaran, 2018). Consequently, the outermost area of the map corresponds to the Pangandaran subdistrict, recognized as the oldest settlement and a central tourism hub, while the innermost observation point is located in Pagergunung Village, considered one of the newest settlements.

Discussion

Language Variation in Pangandaran Regency

In accordance with the scope of this study, the research focuses on lexical variation in Pangandaran Regency, limited to the phonological and lexical levels. Language variation is classified based on the categorization of etyma and their variants (realisations). This classification refers to the linguistic features observed at each point of observation, thereby providing insight into the language situation in the respective areas.

Ayatrohaedi (2002) explains that *berian* refers to the lexical data provided by informants during interviews. In this study, *berian* denotes the vocabulary items directly elicited from the residents of Pangandaran Regency, based on the questionnaire administered during

fieldwork. Variants considered equivalent are marked with slight differences such as lines, dots, or shading, while distinct berian result in different etyma. Etyma is the plural form of etymon, which refers to the root form of a word or morpheme from which other forms may be derived (Munawarah, 2021). In this research, the term etyma refers to both singular and plural lexical forms.

Based on the 317 lexical items on the questionnaire, four etyma groups were identified: one-etymon, two-etymon, three-etymon, and four or more etyma. The one-etymon group includes 63 language maps, the two-etymon group comprises 135 maps, the three-etymon group includes 80 maps, and the four-or-more-etymon group includes 39 maps. These classifications are illustrated in the table below:

Table 3. Etymon Groups Distribution

Etymon	Percentage
1 etymon	20%
2 etimons	43%
3 etimons	25%
≥ 4 etymons	12%

Among the 317 lexical items studied, 63 language maps—or approximately 20%—fall into the one-etymon group. This indicates a degree of linguistic uniformity among several observation points. A notable finding within this group is the berian [kiyeʔ], spoken by communities in the northwest and southwest parts of Pangandaran Regency, specifically in TP2 and TP11. TP11 borders Ciamis Regency in West Java Province, while TP2 lies adjacent to the Indian Ocean. This is particularly interesting since [kiyeʔ] is a known form in Javanese (Sumantri et al., 1985), yet both observation points are distant from Cilacap, Central Java—where Javanese is predominantly spoken. This supports findings from (Wagiati & Zein, 2020), which suggest traces of Javanese migration in Pangandaran. Additionally, the geographical characteristics of TP2 and TP11—forested and mountainous—render them relatively isolated, which may explain the preservation of Javanese vocabulary in these regions. Interviews with local residents and representatives from the Department of Tourism and Culture in Pangandaran indicate that the Javanese population in the region migrated from Kebumen, Central Java. Arifudin (2018) confirms that the Javanese in Kebumen speak the Banyumasan dialect, further suggesting that the use of Javanese in Pangandaran is influenced not only by proximity to Cilacap, but also by historical migration patterns.

Another interesting case involves the berian [kiyö], used at a single observation point, TP6. According to local accounts, TP6 is part of the Sundanese-speaking area. It borders TP2 (a Javanese-speaking area) as well as TP7 and TP23 (Sundanese-speaking areas). The berian [kiyö] is suspected to be a borrowing from Javanese, likely derived from [kiyeʔ] with the final vowel [ɛ] replaced by [ö], aligning with the Sundanese vowel system, which includes the vowel [ö]. This lexical adaptation may result from geographic proximity and sustained interaction between the two languages, promoting lexical borrowing over time.

The two-etymon group comprises the largest number of maps—135, or approximately 43%—which may indicate the presence of two distinct language systems within Pangandaran Regency. A notable finding in this group is the berian [basöh], which appears in 20 observation points, indicating a predominance of Sundanese speakers in the region. Conversely, the berian [tələs] appears in only five observation points—TP2, TP5, TP12, TP13, and TP20—but these are distributed across various areas of the regency, including the northeast, southeast, southwest, and central regions. This scattered distribution suggests that Javanese speakers in Pangandaran are not concentrated in a single area. As mentioned in the background section, this distribution may be linked to historical factors. The Pokok-Pokok Pikiran Pemajuan Kebudayaan Kabupaten Pangandaran (2018) notes that many Javanese settlers in the region historically lived along former railway lines. In the early 20th century, a wave of Javanese migration occurred in conjunction with railway construction projects (Indira et al., 2019). Although these railways are now defunct, Javanese communities still reside along the former tracks, forming ethnolinguistic enclaves.

Another linguistic observation within this group concerns the vowel variation [u] and [ʊ], which may indicate dialectal differences within Javanese. The variety spoken in Pangandaran falls under the Banyumasan dialect (Tohari et al., 2014), which generally uses the high, close vowel [u]. However, this study identifies both [u] and [ʊ] variants. The form [biyuŋ] and [induŋ], featuring [u], are found in TP5, TP13, TP20, and TP22, while the variant [biyoŋ], with [ʊ], is used in TP2 and TP12. This suggests that Javanese spoken in TP2 and TP12 may have been influenced by another Javanese dialect. Interestingly, Sundanese also predominantly uses the [u] vowel, not [ʊ].

According to Figure 3, 80 language maps (25%) belong to the three-etymon group, indicating relatively higher levels of linguistic diversity across observation points. A noteworthy case is the berian [gəmək], used in TP17 and TP23—areas identified by locals as Sundanese-speaking. According to the Kamus Bahasa Sunda-Indonesia (Sumantri et al., 1985), the standard Sundanese word for ‘fat’ is lintuh, suggesting that [gəmək] may be an Indonesian borrowing. Similar patterns appear in the glosses for DOG, SEW, and FAR: the gloss for DOG includes [anjiŋ], [asu], and [gəgək]; SEW includes [kaput], [dəndəm], and [jahit]; and FAR includes [jauh], [adəh], and [təbih]. Forms such as [gəgək], [kaput], and [təbih] are Sundanese (Sumantri et al., 1985); [asu], [dəndəm], and [adəh] are Javanese (Tohari et al., 2014); and [anjiŋ], [jahit], and [jauh] appear to be Indonesian. The prevalence of Indonesian vocabulary in everyday speech in Pangandaran Regency can be attributed to factors such as education and tourism. The language of instruction in schools in Pangandaran Regency is Indonesian. Additionally, Pangandaran Regency is frequently visited by tourists from outside the region because it is a tourist destination. The use of Indonesian in Pangandaran Regency is quite high because the people of Pangandaran prefer to use Indonesian when communicating with visitors. Thus, it is quite possible that the influence of Indonesian is significant in Pangandaran Regency.

Finally, the four-or-more-etymon group comprises 39 language maps (12%). One example is the gloss for LAKE, which includes five berian: [danau], [situ], [waluŋan], [baləŋ], and [tələga]. These variations are influenced by the diverse geographic contexts of the observation points. In interviews, some informants were unfamiliar with the concept of

a lake despite being shown photographs. In such cases, they provided words like [waluʝan] (river) and [baluʝ] (fishpond), based on their closest conceptual equivalents. According to the *Kamus Bahasa Sunda-Indonesia* (Sumantri et al., 1985), [waluʝan] refers to a river and [baluʝ] to a pond. These lexical mismatches reflect local environmental realities, which in turn contribute to the irregular distribution patterns observed on the language maps.

Sociolinguistic Influences and Language Contact

Boberg et al. (Munawarah, 2021) state that isogloss bundles can be used to determine language boundaries and support dialectometric analysis. Based on the dominant isogloss lines observed in the maps, the distribution of lexical variation in Pangandaran Regency can be described. The isogloss bundles indicate dense accumulations in four areas: the northeast, southeast, south-central, and southwest regions. The first thickening of isoglosses appears between observation points TP12–TP13 and TP4, TP18, and TP14 in the northeastern region. TP12 and TP13 are Javanese-speaking areas, while TP4, TP18, and TP14 are Sundanese-speaking. This pattern reflects a substantial lexical difference between Javanese and Sundanese.

Second, a concentration of isoglosses is also observed in the southeast, between TP5 (a Javanese-speaking area) and TP15 (a Sundanese-speaking area). Furthermore, thick isoglosses surround TP20, clearly delineating it as a Javanese-speaking area amidst predominantly Sundanese-speaking surroundings. Another notable accumulation appears in the southwest, where isoglosses form an arc that separates TP2 (a Javanese-speaking area) from the neighboring Sundanese-speaking observation points.

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The dense stacking of isoglosses in several regions suggests a high degree of lexical variation in Pangandaran Regency. This phenomenon is largely driven by the dispersion of Javanese communities across the region, resulting in observable lexical divergence at specific observation points. Lexical variation is distributed across six etyma groups, with the two-etymon group accounting for the largest number of variants. The dominance of glosses in the two-etymon group strengthens the hypothesis that two main languages—Sundanese and Javanese—are spoken in Pangandaran Regency.

Lexical variation is most prominent in the eastern part of the regency, particularly the northeast and southeast regions, which border Cilacap Regency in Central Java. Since Cilacap is a Javanese-speaking area, its proximity may explain the spread of Javanese communities into eastern Pangandaran. Additionally, high lexical variation is observed in the southwestern part of the regency, where only one observation point (TP2) is Javanese-speaking. Interestingly, this area is located far from the Javanese-speaking center in Cilacap. It is also geographically isolated, surrounded by forests and difficult to access due to poor road conditions.

Upon closer examination of the isogloss distribution, another dense accumulation of isoglosses surrounds a single observation point located slightly south-central. This is particularly noteworthy, as the area is a Javanese-speaking enclave entirely surrounded by Sundanese-speaking communities.

These findings reinforce the claims of Indira et al. (2019) regarding the migration of Javanese people to Pangandaran in the early 20th century, which was driven by employment opportunities on coconut plantations and the opening of a railway line to the region.

The map of decommissioned railway lines in Pangandaran shows that the rail network once extended from the north to the east, continuing along the southern region toward the southwest. Specifically, the lines passed through Kalipucang, Sidamulih, and Cijulang Districts. This pattern aligns with the isogloss distribution, as thick isogloss clusters are found at observation points located in these districts. Thus, the concentration of isogloss bundles seen in the comprehensive map above highlights the presence and spread of Javanese in Pangandaran Regency.

In conclusion, it can be inferred that the majority of the population in Pangandaran Regency speaks Sundanese, as reflected in 20 observation points. Meanwhile, only five observation points represent areas inhabited by Javanese-speaking communities: Kertamukti Village (TP2), Pamotan Village (TP5), Kertajaya Village (TP12), Maruyungsari Village (TP13), and Wonoharjo Village (TP20).

The distribution of lexical variation across the regency also aligns with known patterns of migration and language contact. Several villages with Javanese-derived vocabulary are located in the eastern and southwestern parts of the regency, consistent with historical records indicating the settlement of Javanese communities in the early 20th century. Meanwhile, language contact is particularly evident in the transition zones where Javanese-speaking communities interact closely with Sundanese speakers. In these areas, lexical borrowing, code-switching, and even lexical convergence are common.

The borrowing of Indonesian vocabulary in Pangandaran Regency can be understood as language contact resulting from educational and tourism factors. The educational factor here is referred to by (Thomason, 2001) as “learned contact,” that is, language contact caused by the teaching of a single language to a population comprising various ethnic groups so that they can communicate with one another. Thus, the role of Indonesian is to serve as a bridge between the Sundanese, Javanese, and other ethnic groups in Pangandaran Regency. This is further reinforced by the role of Indonesian as the national lingua franca, particularly among the younger generation and in formal settings, such as education and administration. Consequently, the younger generation often prefers to use Indonesian vocabulary in their communication.

In terms of distribution, the highest level of borrowing of Indonesian vocabulary occurs in TP1, namely Pangandaran Village. This is related to the status of Pangandaran Village, which, according to data from the Pangandaran Regency Tourism and Culture Office, has been designated as a tourist hub due to Pangandaran Beach, the primary destination for tourists visiting Pangandaran. As a tourist hub, the majority of residents in Pangandaran Village and nearby villages earn their livelihoods as vendors and tour guides. Both of these occupations require residents to frequently communicate with other ethnic groups as well as tourists. It is this intense and repeated linguistic contact over a long period of time that has led to the Sundanese and Javanese peoples borrowing a significant number of Indonesian vocabulary words. Consequently, the lexical variations in the Pangandaran

language reflect not only traditional dialectal boundaries but also multilingual dynamics and language shift.

Linguistic Isolation and Maintenance in Wonoharjo

Dialectometry is a quantitative method that produces percentage-based results to indicate the degree of variation and determine the linguistic status of regions under dialectological investigation. In this study, dialectometry is employed to examine the linguistic status among various regions in Pangandaran Regency. Based on the matrabahasa triangular map, a total of 62 regional pairings were compared. The matrabahasa triangle map serves as a reference for calculating lexical differences between observation points in the regency. Based on the results of the dialectometric calculation, three percentage categories can be identified:

- a. Percentage $\leq 30\%$: No Difference
- b. Percentage 51%–69% : Dialect Difference
- c. Percentage $\geq 70\%$: Language Difference

Based on the number of observation point comparisons that fall into each category, it can be concluded that there is generally no language difference across Pangandaran Regency. This is primarily due to the dominance of a single language, namely Sundanese. Nevertheless, the dialectometric results also indicate the presence of both dialectal and language differences.

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Dialect differences are observed between TP2 and TP6, TP2 and TP7, TP4 and TP12, and TP13 and TP18. According to community accounts and the Pokok-Pokok Pikiran Pemajuan Kebudayaan Kabupaten Pangandaran (2018), TP2, TP12, and TP13 are Javanese-speaking areas, whereas TP6, TP7, TP4, and TP18 are Sundanese-speaking. However, the dialectometric results suggest that these areas are only dialectally different. This can be attributed to several factors, such as lexical borrowing from neighboring areas and the influence of formal education, which promotes the use of Indonesian in daily communication. In addition, the close proximity between regions facilitates high levels of interaction, which over time can lead to mutual linguistic influence and the blurring of linguistic boundaries.

The results also show language differences within the regency. Such differences are found between TP1 and TP2, TP1 and TP5, TP1 and TP20, TP2 and TP3, TP5 and TP14, TP5 and TP15, TP12 and TP18, TP13 and TP14, TP15 and TP20, TP19 and TP20, TP20 and TP21, and TP20 and TP25. Javanese-speaking communities are found in TP2, TP12, TP13, and TP20, while the remaining observation points are primarily Sundanese-speaking. These findings confirm the presence of two distinct languages—Sundanese and Javanese—within Pangandaran Regency.

In dialectometric analysis, linguistic relationships between observation points are visualised using a spider web map, which is a graphical representation showing the connections between regions based on the degree of lexical difference derived from dialectometric calculations.

Each observation point is placed on the map according to its geographical location and connected by lines based on the calculated degree of linguistic difference. The lines connecting these observation points form a pattern resembling a spider’s web, thereby facilitating researchers in identifying linguistic proximity, the grouping of language variations, and patterns of language distribution within the study area.

The spider web map provides a clearer illustration of linguistic differences. Solid bold lines indicate language differences, dashed lines indicate dialect differences, and dotted lines represent no difference. A particularly interesting case is TP20 (Wonoharjo Village), a Javanese-speaking enclave surrounded by Sundanese-speaking areas: Pangandaran (TP1), Sidamulih (TP21), Parigi (TP25), Banjarharja (TP19), and Bagolo (TP15). Wonoharjo is recognized as an old Javanese village within the regency (Indira et al., 2019). Historically, the presence of Javanese communities in this area is linked to a wave of migration in the early 20th century. During that time, Pangandaran was regarded as an area of natural beauty, fertile land, and abundant employment opportunities—factors that attracted many migrants, including Javanese people. Indira et al. (2019) also explain that the migration was driven by opportunities in coconut plantations and the construction of the Pangandaran railway line. These factors account for the spread of Javanese communities in both the eastern and southwestern parts of the regency, which were along the former railway route.

Further evidence of Wonoharjo’s status as an old Javanese village is the presence of Javanese cultural arts, such as Kuda Lumping, locally known as Ebeg. Ebeg is a traditional horse performance using figures made from cowhide or bamboo, commonly found in the Banyumas Residency region, including Purbalingga, Cilacap, Purwokerto, Kebumen, and Banjarnegara (Indira et al., 2019). Despite being surrounded by Sundanese-speaking communities, the residents of Wonoharjo have retained their Javanese language. Bilingualism and code-switching with Indonesian and Sundanese are common, especially in interethnic communication. This demonstrates a remarkable case of linguistic resilience and cultural maintenance amidst dominant linguistic surroundings.

Conclusion

This study reveals significant lexical variation within Pangandaran Regency, which can be categorized into several etyma groups. These variations demonstrate the influence of two dominant language systems—Sundanese and Javanese—with some degree of lexical borrowing and code-switching involving Indonesian, particularly in interethnic communication contexts.

Findings indicate that, in general, there is minimal linguistic divergence across most observation points in the regency, reflecting the widespread use and dominance of the Sundanese language. However, both dialectal and language-level differences were identified in specific areas, as confirmed through dialectometric analysis. These patterns support the view that Pangandaran constitutes a linguistically dynamic region, shaped by historical migration, intergroup contact, and socio-cultural developments such as education and population mobility.

A particularly noteworthy case is that of Wonoharjo Village (TP20), where, despite being geographically surrounded by Sundanese-speaking areas, the community has successfully maintained its Javanese linguistic identity. This preservation is closely linked to early-20th-century migration patterns and the continued practice of traditional Javanese cultural expressions. The linguistic resilience observed in Wonoharjo illustrates how sustained cultural transmission and adaptive communicative strategies can support minority language maintenance in the context of dominant-language environments.

Overall, the lexical variation observed across Pangandaran Regency is not merely a reflection of linguistic boundaries, but also of broader social dynamics, historical migration trajectories, and patterns of interethnic interaction. As such, linguistic mapping in this context not only serves as a valuable tool for documenting language variation, but also offers insights into the social structure and cultural identities embedded within the local population.

Implications

The findings of this study have several important implications for the fields of dialectology, sociolinguistics, and language policy. First, the identification of lexical variation and language boundaries through isogloss bundles and dialectometric analysis illustrates how spatial linguistic data can reveal deeper social and historical processes such as migration and settlement patterns. The case of Pangandaran Regency demonstrates that language variation is not merely a linguistic phenomenon, but a reflection of cultural contact, mobility, and identity formation.

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Second, the persistence of Javanese-speaking communities within predominantly Sundanese areas—such as in Wonoharjo Village—highlights the importance of community agency in language maintenance. Despite external sociolinguistic pressures, these communities have succeeded in preserving their linguistic heritage, indicating the role of cultural resilience and intergenerational transmission. Such cases challenge simplistic models of language shift and instead advocate for more nuanced understandings of multilingual ecologies.

Lastly, the integration of historical and ethnographic perspectives with quantitative dialectometry enriches linguistic analysis by providing multidimensional insights. The inclusion of factors such as former railway routes, economic opportunities, and traditional arts (e.g., Ebeg) underscores the need for interdisciplinary approaches in analyzing language distribution and vitality.

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